

Pilot Evaluation 4: Matchmaking formats to improve the Una Europa RIR Sharing

Final Version

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Summary:

The aim of this pilot action was to experiment with a matchmaking format that brings together representatives of Una Europa RIs (researchers and RIs managers) to discuss possible paths for opening and sharing infrastructures and establishing collaborations in R&I and education. This RI matchmaking exercise was carried out in the thematic fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health wherein two case studies were defined: Museums and Digital Collections, and Genomics.

The rationale for the pilot action resided in the need to create communities on RIs by connecting and creating networks of researchers and RI managers across the Alliance. Matchmaking events provide the opportunity for researchers and RI managers to get to know each other, share interests, ideas and expertise, and establish collaborations. The pilot addressed the sharing infrastructure and resources transformation module, and indirectly the comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices module.

The first activity of the pilot was to define the scope for each thematic field in agreement with the RIs Cluster, and the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Based on the selected scope, the WP2 team identified the relevant RIs to engage in the pilot, with key Una.Resin stakeholders asked to identify further RIs that may be interested. For each case study, a call for EoIs was launched that targeted the relevant group of RIs through a specific form used to collect basic information, alongside preliminary inputs on needs and expectations of participants. This data was used to shape the workshops' agenda and drive the discussions. The group of RIs that expressed interest were invited to attend two matchmaking workshops, where sessions dedicated to the mutual knowledge of participants were followed by a more specific discussion on mutual interests, ideas for joint actions, collaboration opportunities in relation to self-steering committees' activities, and paths (considering barriers and enablers) towards opening and sharing RIs. The workshop illustrated how developing links with the strategies and action plans of the relevant self-steering committees was key, as was empowering infrastructures to offer their own proposals and visions. The output was a report that presented ideas for undertaking concrete actions in the short, medium, and long run.

The pilot has achieved important **outcomes** through the implementation of the matchmaking format in the Cultural Heritage and One Health fields. The primary achievement is the establishment of networks consisting of RIs managers and responsible researchers in the field of Museums and Digital collections, and Genomics. The workshops allowed participants to connect with each other and, in doing so, understand their specificities and needs and define their mutual interests. The pilot project illustrated how establishing a network of RIs goes beyond the mere exchange of experiences and best practices and fosters joint collaborative activities (including research or educational projects) based on the impetus provided by

researchers. Another important outcome of the pilot is the establishment of the direct connections between participating RIs and the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Both self-steering committees expressed interest in taking forward the collaboration with RIs in the framework of Una.Futura.

The connection between the participating RIs and the self-steering committees holds multiple benefits and prospective impacts. Firstly, it enables the RIs to support activities that will be validated as part of the Una.Futura project action plan, whilst empowering RIs to bring their own vision and suggest their own collaboration activities for research enhancement. In a long-term perspective, empowering RIs as actors of international collaboration could transform the institutional vision of infrastructure from solely being a support system, with RIs also being perceived as a driving force behind research activities. This change in perception could help improve the valorisation of RIs, and both encourage and support policy makers in developing global solutions on openness and shareability.

The key **lessons learnt** from the pilot are as follows: 1) matchmaking workshops enable the establishment and strengthening of networks, laying the basis for fruitful collaborations; 2) continuing and scaling up of the workshops to different types of RIs, disciplines, and Focus Areas is crucial for creating a knowledge community of RIs; 3) identifying mutual interest and implementing joint activities is a crucial step for the opening up and potential sharing of RIs; 4) collaborations forged through workshops and matchmaking activities can serve as a springboard for joint research projects, collaborative grants, and educational initiatives; and 5) the alignment and synergy between the Una Europa's Focus Areas and RIs are essential for unlocking the full potential of collaboration. By identifying areas of convergence, Una Europa could leverage the expertise and resources of RIs to address the challenges and research questions within the Focus Areas.

The most important recommendations are related to the development of an improved and consolidated matchmaking format with the view of continuation and scaling-up, which was also suggested in the Una Europa Strategy for Sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). Planning a series of workshops dedicated to RIs presentations and discussions is highly recommended to aid matchmaking. It would also be useful to build in time for small-group workshops/seminars that address specific issues (e.g., costing and funding models; Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable (FAIR) data management) or for sharing knowledge and expertise on topics of common interest, since these could further facilitate discussion. A digital platform – including articles, newsletters, and success stories – could be created to facilitate the connection among RIs representatives and give visibility to activities across the network. Representatives from the Una Europa self-steering committees should be present during the workshops in order to provide the necessary context and information on the framework of the Focus Area activities. It is also important to find synergies with other collaborative actions of the Alliance, including educational programmes.

Objectives and aims of the pilot

The aim of this pilot action was to experiment with a matchmaking format that brings together representatives of Una Europa RIs (researchers and RIs managers) to discuss possible paths for opening and sharing infrastructures and establishing collaborations in R&I and education. This RI matchmaking exercise was carried out in the thematic fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health, wherein two case studies were defined: Museums and Digital Collections, and

Genomics. The pilot project aimed to address the “Sharing Infrastructure and Resources” transformation model. Considering the involvement of data infrastructures and the topics addressed in the workshop discussions, the pilot also indirectly contributed to the “Comprehensive mainstreaming of Open Science practices” transformation module.

The barriers to cross-border and cross-sectoral R&I collaboration addressed by the pilot are the following:

- Lack of mutual knowledge of assets, expertise, and services related to RIRs available in each university of Una Europa and relevant to different disciplinary fields.
- Lack of mutual knowledge on interests and activities, and low awareness of collaboration opportunities in research, education, and innovation connected to the activities of the self-steering committees of Una Europa.
- Lack of opportunities for sharing knowledge, experiences, and practices on topics of common interest, including theme-specific topics (e.g., related to protocols, technologies, etc.), as well as cross-cutting issues such as costing and funding models and Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable (FAIR) management of data infrastructure.
- Lack of a network and of consistent exchange between the personnel working on RIs (including researchers and RIs managers), with bottom-up participatory processes promoting sharing of knowledge and experiences among RIs representatives being crucial to enable a prospective opening and sharing of RIs across the Alliance.

This pilot aims to foster Open Science and open access to scientific results and data (e.g., online open notebooks, OERs, open data, etc.), whilst also encouraging an opening and sharing of RIs. In doing so, the pilot seeks to support a desired institutional change towards opening and sharing. To support the achievement of this change, the intended audiences of the pilot project are:

- In the short term: Universities in general, research performing organisation, researchers, and professional staff of RIs.
- In the medium/long term: Universities in general, research performing organisations, researchers, research and development businesses and industry, citizens, NGOs, and professional staff of RIs.

The beneficiaries of the pilot are as follows:

- In the short term: Researchers, RI managers, teaching staff, and students.
- In the medium/long term: Researchers, teaching staff and students, RI managers and experts, funding and policy officers, non-academic stakeholders (businesses, cultural organisations, etc.), citizens, other universities, and European University Alliances.

In the design phase, a synergy was sought with the pilot action implemented within WP1 in the field of One Health (i.e., Pilot Evaluation 1 in this document). The One Health self-steering committee suggested that WP2 could test the matchmaking format on the RIs involved in the proposals that were being developed in the framework of the WP1 pilot action. The WP2 team explored the possibility of setting up a matchmaking exercise in connection with a proposal on Cluster 6 of Horizon Europe, related to the theme of Biodiversity and with a view to laying the basis for the creation of an RIs network in this field. However, the discussion among potential partners did not lead to the preparation of a proposal. Therefore, the synergy between the two pilot projects did not materialise. In general, it is worth noting that there are similarities in the

underlying concepts of the two pilot actions, notably the importance of “connecting people”, i.e., creating formats and opportunities of matchmaking targeted to the research community of the Alliance to develop projects or other forms of collaborations.

A meaningful synergy was established between the Una.Resin WP2 and the RiTrain Plus project. The joint workshop with RiTrainPlus (Bologna, October 2022) highlighted the importance of collaborating on training programmes that prepare future managers and operators of European RIs and Core Facilities, and to enable the continued training of those who already hold such positions. Training was one of main needs that emerged during the pilot, and it was discussed by participants from both the Cultural Heritage and One Health field. The collaboration between the Una Europa Focus Areas and RiTrain Plus was also discussed in June 2023 in Leiden and will be taken forward in collaboration with the interested self-steering committees.

Initial design and implementation of the pilot project

One of the key inputs emerging from the mapping exercise initiated at the start of Una.Resin, which was also further discussed during the co-creation workshop, was the need to create communities on RIs. This element is considered in the specific objectives and actions proposed in Pillar 1 “Promoting openness of RIs and data infrastructures to foster research collaboration” of Deliverable 2.2, and became the main objective of the pilot actions that were designed and tested by WP2. WP2 developed a pilot action that addressed the need to creating communities on RIs by connecting (i.e., creating networks of) researchers, RIs managers, and experts across the Alliance to give them the opportunity to get to know each other, share knowledge, interests, ideas and expertise, and initiate collaborations.

The matchmaking exercise among RIs was carried out in the thematic fields of Cultural Heritage and One Health, with the specific case studies, Museums and Digital Collections and Genomics, chosen in collaboration with the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee and the RI Cluster. The matchmaking format thus targeted representatives of RIs in these two thematic fields and brought together academics, managers, and technicians to discuss possible paths for opening and sharing infrastructures and for exploring new collaborations in R&I and education. The need to connecting people is closely linked to the need to develop common tools for sharing information on the RIs available across Una Europa universities, which is the focus of the other WP2 pilot action (Pilot Evaluation 3 in this document).

The first step of the pilot action was defining the scope of each thematic field in agreement with the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Based on the selected scope, the WP2 team identified the relevant RIs that could be involved using the list of infrastructures that participated in the mapping exercise and the participants of the WP2 co-creation workshop as the starting point. These lists were the main data sources used to identify the RIs potentially interested in the pilot action.¹ In addition, the Una.Resin Project Managers, the members of the RI Cluster and the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees were asked to identify further RIs that could be potentially interested in joining the

¹ The participation in the pilot action was as follows: for Museums and Digital Collections, 31 researchers/RIs managers from 9 universities (including the University of Zurich and the University of Paris-Nanterre) expressed interest in the pilot representing 27 infrastructures, and 22 RIs were involved in the two workshops; and for Genomics, 17 researchers/RIs managers from 6 universities (including the University of Zurich) expressed interest in the pilot representing 11 infrastructures, and 10 RIs were involved in the two workshops.

pilot process.

During the implementation of the pilot action, preliminary data was collected from representatives of RIs that expressed interest in participating in the matchmaking workshops. The following data collected (through a google form) in the registration phase:

- Name of the RI represented;
- Short description of the RI;
- If the infrastructure represented completed a questionnaire as part of the Una.Resin mapping exercise and/or participated in the co-creation workshop held in June 2022;
- If the infrastructure represented is already open (i.e., accessible) to local, national or international partners including external academics but also non-academics;
- If the infrastructure represented already has plans to open and share services at local, national or international level;
- What support (e.g., training, funds, visibility, etc.) is needed to help share and open your infrastructure; and
- What the expectations are in relation to the participation in the workshops.

The data provided by the participants was analysed and presented during the first workshop for both case studies. For the case study “Museums and Digital Collections”, the majority of infrastructures had participated in the Una.Resin mapping exercise and/or in the WP2 co-creation workshop, while this was not the case for the “Genomics” infrastructures. In both case studies, the majority of infrastructures declared their openness to local, national or international partners and that they had plans regarding opening and sharing of services. In terms of needs, funding for training, staff exchange, IT development, collaboration and visibility were all highlighted. Participants expectations for the pilot action were as follows: exchange of best practices and mutual learning, collaboration and networking, joint proposal development, joint research, and visibility. This preliminary data was taken into account in the discussion that took place during the workshops. The outcomes of the workshops were shared with the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees, with both committees including the objective to continue collaborating with RIs in the Una.Futura framework in their Strategy and Action Plan.

In conclusion, a very inclusive and bottom-up approach was adopted in the process of designing and implementing the pilot action. Collaboration with, and gaining feedback from, stakeholders (self-steering committees, pilot participants, RI Cluster, Una.Resin project managers) was key in all phases of the pilot and led to a positive follow-up of the action itself.

The pilot action carried out in the field of Cultural Heritage was planned and implemented with the substantial contribution of the RI Cluster members and the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee. The methodology was defined in collaboration with the cluster members and they also supported with the workshop preparation. Furthermore, RI Cluster members actively encouraged involvement from RIs within their universities.

The Cultural Heritage self-steering committee defined the scope of the pilot action addressing Museums and Digital collections. The pilot action was then implemented through two workshops aimed at promoting matchmaking, networking, and community building across the Una Europa Museums and Digital collections, with a view to fostering mutual knowledge,

exploring collaborations, and developing concrete ways of opening and sharing infrastructures across the Alliance. The chair of the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee was actively involved in the conception and moderation of the two workshops named “Sharing Una Europa infrastructures: Museums and Digital collections” (30th of March and 4th of May 2023). During the first workshop, participants presented their infrastructures and expertise and discussed their mutual interests. In the second workshop participants discussed their interests in relation to the draft action plan developed by the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee in the framework of the Una.Futura project. Specific relevance was given to the project aimed at creating a Virtual Museum of the heritage of Una Europa universities. The objective to collaborate systematically with the RIs involved in Una.Resin was integrated in the Strategy and Action Plan subsequently developed by the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee.

Regarding the implementation of the pilot action in the field of One Health, the RI Cluster members were involved in the planning phase and supported with defining the methodology, as well as in the preparation and moderation of the workshops. RI Cluster members were inputted into defining the scope of the Genomics pilot action. During the WP2 co-creation workshop, this topic emerged as one of the most interesting in terms of available facilities, expertise, and potential collaborations. The workshops were chaired by the UEDIN representative in the RI Cluster in collaboration with the WP2 team. Even though the One Health self-steering committee did not participate directly in the workshops, the outcomes were shared with the committee and ideas for a possible follow-up were discussed, such as the importance of having a more in-depth understanding of the expertise and strengths of each institution. The Strategy and Action plan developed in the framework of the Una.Futura project referenced the sharing of RIs (such as Genomics core facilities) and providing RIs in the field of One Health with increased visibility to the Una.Resin WP2 pilot format.

During the workshops scenarios for collaborating and opening/sharing RIs were discussed by participants in both fields. The RIs representatives appreciated for the opportunity to meet their colleagues in other universities. However, without any certainties regarding funding, it was challenging to design and plan concrete actions that would guarantee the sustainability of the network and support its collaboration activities. In this regard, it is very positive that the self-steering committees have already expressed their interest both in engaging RIs in their Strategy and Action plan and taking forward some actions (e.g., Virtual Museum of the Una Europa universities heritage) in the framework of the Una.Futura project. However, as highlighted in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, dedicated funding and resource for interconnecting RIs (i.e., for network creation) would be needed to sustain and scale up the piloted matchmaking format. Creating a Una Europa RIs community through networking and matchmaking in thematic areas (also supported by physical mobility) is a prerequisite for concretely sharing and opening RIs. Yet, carrying out bottom-up processes of stakeholders’ engagement is resource and time intensive, and there is a that risk these activities will not be systematic and sustainable without dedicated funding.

Another important challenge was related to the difficulty of addressing the complexity of the Una Europa RIs landscape. The mapping carried out in the first phase of the project, as well as the active collaboration of stakeholders, provided a solid basis for involving RIs in an inclusive manner. However, Una Europa institutions are large, comprehensive universities, which makes it difficult to have a complete and up to date overview of infrastructures and expertise and to keep stakeholders engaged. In this regard, it is crucial to develop digital tools

to share information (see WP2 pilot action “blueprint for a common catalogue of research infrastructures” in this document) and platforms that can facilitate engagement and dialogue among stakeholders.

Outcomes and impact of the pilot project

Implementation of the matchmaking format in the Cultural Heritage and One Health field has achieved several important outcomes. The primary achievement of these workshops is the establishment of networks consisting of RIs managers, experts, and responsible researchers in the field of Museums and Digital Collections, and Genomics. These workshops allowed the participants to become familiar with each other, understand their specificities and needs, and define their mutual interests.

Under the guidance of the WP2 team, the established network goes beyond a mere collection of contacts to serve as a reflection-oriented network. In the long run, the hope is that the network will serve as a solution-oriented network. During the workshops, participants have not only reflected on possible partnerships and collaborations, but also opened their minds to new forms of collaboration that extend beyond the established frameworks and target the creation of a barrier-free research ecosystem. As a result, the pilot project raised the participants' awareness about the importance of opening RIs and the need to reflect on the openness and shareability of their data and services. The pilot also sought to inspire the opening up to international partners and cooperation on a European level, despite the represented infrastructures being small to medium in size.

The pilot project illustrated how establishing a network of RIs goes beyond the mere exchange of experiences and best practices and fosters joint collaborative activities (including research or educational projects) based on the impetus provided by researchers. Another important outcome of the pilot is, therefore, the establishment of the direct connection between participating RIs and the Una Europa self-steering committees. Even though the involvement of the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees were different during the implementation phase, both expressed interest in taking forward the collaboration with RIs in the framework of Una.Futura.

The connection between the participating RIs and the self-steering committees holds multiple benefits and prospective impacts. Firstly, it enables the RIs to support activities that will be validated as part of the Una.Futura project action plan, whilst empowering RIs to bring their own vision and suggest their own collaboration activities for research enhancement. In a long-term perspective, empowering RIs as actors of international collaboration could transform the institutional vision of infrastructure from solely being a support system, with them also being perceived as a driving force behind research activities. This change in perception can help improve the valorisation of RIs, and both encourage and support policy makers in developing global solutions on openness and shareability.

In summary, the initial outcomes of the pilot project have demonstrated a high level of interest from RIs regarding collaboration and the potential for scaling up. The success of this pilot indicates that repeating and expanding such projects can generate interest from other types of infrastructures and other scientific domains. Moreover, the alignment of the initiatives discussed during the workshops with the self-steering committees' action plans holds great

potential for reinforcing the research ecosystem and positioning RIs more effectively within institutional policies.

The pilot project has successfully achieved its stated goals and outcomes and laid the basis for promoting a barrier-free collaboration in R&I. In both case studies, many ideas for collaboration in R&I, but also in education, emerged and as mentioned above, the self-steering committees have already taken some of these actions forward in the framework of Una.Futura. Moreover, this pilot action strongly contributed to raising awareness on the importance of RIs as enablers of a barrier-free R&I ecosystem, and a systematic collaboration with RIs is now included as a strategic objective in the Strategy and Action Plans of the both the Culture Heritage and One Health self-steering committee.

Concerning the pilot on Museums and Digital collections, various ideas for collaboration between RIs and the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee emerged. These include:

- Creating a "virtual museum" to showcase the RIs and their collections, hence providing visibility to their assets. This initiative could serve as an alternative to a joint catalogue, considering that most RIs already have their own online catalogues or are part of broader national or European catalogue initiatives.
- Supporting Una Europa's participation in other projects such as the Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KIC) (European Institute of Innovation & Technology (EIT) Culture & Creativity), as well as fostering important external partnerships with organisations and projects like ARCHE, European Heritage Hub, Europeana, Nemo, etc.
- Participating in joint calls, such as "A European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage," which aims to develop RIs and their tools.
- Contributing to the organisation of joint events like the European Academic Heritage Day or the European Archaeology Days.
- Facilitating the exchange of best practices, particularly in collaborating with non-academic partners such as NGOs, institutions, businesses, and the wider civil society.

In addition to these collaborative actions, research and educational activities were also considered. For research, several joint actions and ideas were discussed:

- Positioning RIs as catalysts for new research projects and research activities, including PhD research. Specific calls could be launched to study RI collections or methodologies such as conservation, digitisation, AI imaging, and more. Una Europa RIs can provide support and inspiration to Transnational Research Teams (TRTs) established within the framework of Cultural Heritage Doctoral programs.
- Supporting Una Europa Cultural Heritage initiatives in expanding their research topics to include Asia, Africa, and Latin America, as well as other interdisciplinary research projects aligned with Una Europa's Focus Areas.
- Assisting researchers in publishing their research as open access and facilitating joint publication initiatives.
- Hosting or participating in scientific conferences on relevant subjects.

In terms of promoting the use of RIs in educational activities, collaboration between RIs and the Cultural Heritage self-steering committee can yield fruitful results:

- RIs can propose trainings or courses to develop specific skills, such as digitisation,

imaging, data modelling, open-science policies related to cultural heritage, and specialised humanities disciplines, 3D representations, AI applied to forms/images, study of ancient materials, and more. These trainings/courses could be offered as massive-open-online courses (MOOCs) or summer schools.

- Integrating these courses into existing PhD programs or incorporating them into future Bachelor's and Master's programs.

Concerning the pilot on Genomics, the ideas that emerged, and the following resulting recommendations, are key for the Alliance to move towards opening and sharing RIs and, ultimately, build a barrier-free research ecosystem:

- Develop tools to allow the research community to learn and explore the range of RIs available across the Alliance and provide a common information point. This will allow complementary assets to be identified and enhance RI visibility to potential users and collaborators.
- Connect people to promote contact across RI staff and with academic researchers, and matchmaking for RIs in specific research domains. This can take the form of articles, newsletters, and success stories that can be shared through digital platforms.
- Enhance the role of RI in fostering Open Research and FAIR data management, work on the development of common guidelines on operationalisation of FAIR principles.
- Assess costing and funding models, secure funding in order to cover access fees, stimulate researchers applying for grants to cover RI costs, and allocate seed-funding for initial research collaborations. It would be important to adapt pricing systems and business models for Alliance members by taking multiple perspectives into account (e.g., government regulations and user perspectives). The difficulty in managing different expectations on costing from different stakeholders (i.e., users, institutional funders, and funding agencies) was highlighted as a critical point.
- Strengthening knowledge and skills in RI management, e.g., through mutual learning, training, and micro-credentials. As previously mentioned, there is an interest to promote staff mobility and interdisciplinary research, and to work very closely with the One Health self-steering committee to integrate the proposed actions into their visions and objectives.
- Create policies and strategies to overcoming barriers, such as the co-design and promotion of an Una Europa charter for RIs that will encourage the adoption of common general principles. This can be concretised through undertaking a common advocacy action to strengthen RIs.

The project was based on a solid methodology and piloted a simple “start-up process” for establishing a network of RIs that could be applied to different thematic fields and different types of infrastructures. The process can be summarised as follows:

- Definition of the scope (e.g., theme, type of RIs, type of technology, etc.) in alignment with the self-steering committee interests and activities, and also in collaboration with RI experts.
- Identification of relevant RIs that could be involved based on a mapping process and on the consultation with key stakeholders.
- Launch of a call for EoIs targeting the relevant group of RIs representatives (academics and RIs managers). The EoI should be launched through a specific form used to collect basic information but also preliminary inputs on needs and expectations of participants.

This data can then be used to shape the workshops' agenda and drive the discussions.

- The group of interested RIs are invited to attend a series of matchmaking workshops that lay the basis for establishing a network. The first step will be mutual knowledge of participants, followed by a more specific discussion on mutual interests, ideas for joint actions and collaborations in relation to self-steering committees' activities, and paths (considering barriers and enablers) towards opening and sharing RIs. Discussion could be supported by Miro boards and organised in breakout rooms.
- The first output could be a report/roadmap for undertaking concrete actions in the short, medium, and long run (and specifying the resources needed). The link with relevant self-steering committees as Una Europa Interdisciplinary Hubs is key, but infrastructures should also be empowered to bring their own proposals and visions.
- As recommended in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, it is crucial to seek funding for the sustainability and scaling up of the activities.

The format of this process does not require specific tools and, therefore, is easily accessible and transferable. All the materials (data on mapped RIs; call for EoIs; Google form; materials related to the workshops, final reports) are available to Una.Resin teams and the RI Cluster. These materials can be considered as an initial toolkit that can be used to scale up the format in other thematic fields, taking into consideration the lessons learnt from Una.Resin.

The outcomes of this pilot project informed the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2), where the need to create a RIs community is strongly underlined. The recommendations of the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2 were shared with the institutional decision-makers of the Una Europa universities, and the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group approved the project deliverables and recognised the importance of the Una.Resin strategies. In particular, the Una Europa Research and Innovation Strategy (Una.Resin Deliverable 1.2) and the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan for Sharing Research Infrastructures and Resources (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2) informed the vision on the transversal theme on R&I of the Una.Futura project.

In parallel, a two-phase survey was launched within the Alliance to prioritise R&I actions and allocate resources for implementation. In this framework, institutional decision makers are evaluating the possibility to take forward the matchmaking format piloted as part of the Una.Resin project, creating thematic networks of infrastructures that can collaborate and find ways of sharing services and facilities. This action would strengthen the visibility of small-medium scaled university infrastructures towards external users (including non-academic users and the civil society).

In the future, this action could influence decision-makers at the European level. It promotes decisions advancing the development of specific funding calls dedicated to supporting bottom-up networking and community-building processes as a prerequisite for sharing and opening infrastructures. Thus, the action could foster the development of decisions that strengthen the connection and integration of the RI ecosystem of the Alliances.

Sustainability of the pilot project

At this stage, it is still not precisely defined when the insights and outcomes delivered through the pilot project will be continued or replicated/scaled up. As mentioned, the self-steering

committees are in the process of finalising their Strategy and Action plans in the framework of the Una.Futura project. Systematic collaboration with RIs based on the outcomes of the Una.Resin activities is already included in the action plans of the Cultural Heritage and One Health self-steering committees. Some specific actions, such as the creation of a Virtual Museum of Una Europa universities heritage, will be undertaken in Una.Futura and will engage the research and data infrastructures that have been involved in the Una.Resin pilot. By mapping and bringing together digital collections from all the Una Europa universities, the pilot project inspired the prospective creation of a new, shared virtual museum of the (tangible and intangible) academic heritage of Una Europa universities based on the sharing of digital infrastructures. The virtual museum will not be a mere additional database, but will be focused on infrastructural development and the creation of tools and applications that will foster new display formats of preserved digital material for various forms of storytelling.

In general, the engagement of RIs and data infrastructures in the self-steering committees' research and education activities is key to ensure sustained and committed development that build on the insights and outcomes of the pilot action. Since the action plans are specific for each Focus Area, it is likely that the type and level of RIs engagement will vary across Focus Areas and across institutions.

In relation to the continuation, and possible scaling, of the matchmaking format piloted in Una.Resin, it is important to consider that this action is part of the Una Europa Strategy and Action Plan on sharing RIRs (Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2). In this document, the proposed action, named "Creating a RIs Community" (see Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, Pillar 1 – Action 2), is focused on theme-specific matchmaking workshops and events for RIs and, at higher levels of ambition, the creation of thematic networks of RIs and scaling to other Focus Areas, and, in the long run, towards possible synergies with other alliances.

The priorities and actions on research and data infrastructures proposed in the Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2 have informed the Una Europa R&I Vision and are now being assessed for prioritisation by the governance of the Una Europa institutions. More specifically, a prioritisation exercise at the higher decision-making levels of the Alliance has been launched in relation to potential future activities in the area of R&I. This exercise is based on a matrix of potential actions, including the priorities on infrastructures proposed in Una.Resin Deliverable 2.2, which will be ranked through a two-stage survey; the preferred level of ambition and resource allocation for the prioritised actions will also be defined. The outcomes of this exercise will inform the development of a common R&I action plan for the Alliance. This plan will be discussed by the Board of Directors and Research Strategy Group and, based on a clear agreement on the prioritised actions and resources to be committed, actions will either be implemented under the framework of Una.Futura, with institutional resources, or with institutional resources focused on attracting external funding.

As explained above, ensuring the connection between RIs and self-steering committees, and finalising the Una Europa prioritisation exercise of R&I actions (including the continuation and scaling up of RIs matchmaking format) is key to assess the feasibility of scaling up the pilot project beyond the Una.Resin project. The format is easily accessible based on the available materials and lessons learnt. This initial toolkit will enable the continuation of the matchmaking process and empower RIs to initiate and lead workshops autonomously. In this respect, it is important to underline that there was an initial interest expressed by a UEDIN representative

in the RI Cluster to start a RIs network in the field of Mass Spectrometry via the matchmaking format (this action has not been undertaken yet).

The continuation and scaling up of the matchmaking format piloted in Una.Resin would lead to a consolidation of a methodology that could also be of interest to other alliances. In a longer perspective, joint matchmaking events could be organised at national and European levels to scale up the RIs cooperation. In order to guarantee the sustainability of the format, it is crucial to ensure an effective communication and valorisation of collaborative activities among RIs. Una Europa should provide visibility to the thematic networks of infrastructures through its communication channels, to promote awareness and engagement among relevant stakeholders. Moreover, to further stimulate systematic and sustainable bottom-up matchmaking and community-building activities, a dedicated funding call from the EC would be needed, specifically aimed at connecting RIs and creating theme-focused networks of RIs (between universities, alliances but also with ESFRI infrastructures). Funding for organising in-person seminars, workshops, and events and to support physical attendance would be key to supporting the sustainability of this pilot action.

In terms of cost-benefits analysis, it is important to consider that bottom-up engagement processes require a lot of resources but yield a high benefit return. Una.Resin WP2 pioneered the Alliance work on RIs and, in the initial phases of this work (mapping and co-creation workshop), the first and most important topic that emerged was the need of researchers and RIs managers to know each other's available assets, expertise, and interests. This was the rationale behind the choice of a bottom-up participatory format, focused on specific case studies with a scalable methodology. This required a high degree effort and, due to the limited resources, only two "start-up" workshops were organised per each case study. This initial community-building exercise helped create awareness among RIs stakeholders about the assets of other universities, as well as an awareness of opportunities for collaboration across the Alliance. These bottom-up processes, and the concrete collaborations among RIs that arose, represent a crucial step for supporting interdisciplinary research addressing complex challenges and for moving towards opening and sharing RIs across the Alliance. National and European policymakers should invest in these processes by allocating dedicated funding to Alliances (and more in general, universities) and supporting the development of a more connected and integrated ecosystem of RIs via decision-making and policy.

Lessons learnt

A series of lessons have been identified from designing and implementing this pilot:

- The format of the pilot project was successful. Workshops enabled the establishment and strengthening of networks of RIs and created opportunities for participants to exchange ideas, explore potential partnerships, and identify areas of common interest that can lead to fruitful collaborations.
- Continuing and scaling up the workshops to different types, disciplines, and Focus Areas is crucial for creating a knowledge community of RIs. This can lead to the formation of interdisciplinary teams that can tackle complex challenges and develop innovative solutions, thus contributing to the implementation of the R&I agenda of the Alliance.
- Identifying mutual interest and implementing joint activities is a crucial step for the opening up and potential sharing of RIs.
- Collaborations forged through workshops and matchmaking activities can extend

beyond initial interactions, and serve as a springboard for joint research projects, collaborative grants, and educational initiatives.

- The alignment and synergy between the Una Europa's Focus Areas and RIs are essential for unlocking the full potential of collaboration. By identifying areas of convergence, we can leverage the expertise and resources of RIs to address the challenges and research questions within the Focus Areas.

Recommendations for the future

The pilot offers a number of recommendations giving direction to future activity:

- Planning a series of workshops dedicated to RIs presentations and discussions. It would also be useful to build in time for workshops/seminars that address specific issues (e.g., costing and funding models; FAIR data management) or for sharing knowledge and expertise on topics of common interest.
- Having small groups (e.g., formed on the basis of RIs type) can facilitate discussions. A digital platform – including articles, newsletters, and success stories – could be created to facilitate the connection among RIs representatives and give visibility to the network activities.
- Representatives from the Una Europa self-steering committees should be present during the workshops in order to provide the necessary context and information on the framework of the Focus Area activities.
- It is important to find synergies with other collaborative actions of the Alliance, including educational programmes.
- It is important to find resources for collaborative activities through the development of joint applications, as well as resources to promote staff mobility for onsite visits, training, and the organisation of physical workshops and events.